

INSURGENCE OF GLAUCOMA

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Abstract

Glaucoma is a group of progressive optic neuropathies and remains one of the leading causes of irreversible blindness worldwide. Characterized by the degeneration of retinal ganglion cells, its onset is often associated with increased intraocular pressure (IOP), although not exclusively. This article explores the historical context, pathophysiology, classification, and current therapeutic approaches to glaucoma, with a focus on primary open-angle and angle-closure subtypes. Emphasis is placed on risk factors such as age, ethnicity, genetic predisposition, and myopia. A clinical case study highlights the psychosocial impact of the disease, particularly regarding vision-related quality of life (VRQoL). While treatment options range from pharmacological and laser therapies to surgical interventions and emerging techniques like gene and stem cell therapy, early detection remains the most critical challenge. The article discusses the limitations of current screening methods and the potential role of polygenic risk scores and artificial intelligence in improving diagnosis and accessibility, especially in underserved populations. Ultimately, the need for improved awareness, targeted screening, and personalized treatment underscores the importance of continued research and innovation in glaucoma care.

Keywords: *glaucoma, blindness, ocular hypertension*

Glaucoma is a group of optic neuropathies representing the leading cause of blindness in developed country, characterized by progressive degeneration of retinal ganglion cells (RGCs). This complex eye disease is commonly associated with an increase of intraocular pressure (IOP), which can lead to vision loss. The earliest description provided regarding similar disease like glaucoma date back to Ancient Greece, where Aristotle and Hippocrates (around 500 AC) used the term *glaukos* to describe an advanced-stage eye disease marked by a gray-green or blue hue of the pupil.^[1,3]

Glaucoma can be categorized based on its origin: primary glaucoma occurs independently as an idiopathic disorder affecting the anterior chamber and optic nerve, whereas secondary glaucoma arises as a complication due to other identifiable predisposing factors. Further classification distinguishes between open-angle glaucoma (OAG) and angle-closure glaucoma.^[1]

A key feature of glaucoma is the interplay between physiological processes occurring in distinct parts of the eye: pressure changes in the anterior segment contribute to damage the posterior segment, particularly the retina.^[3]

The main structures involved in its pathophysiology include the ciliary body, the anterior chamber and the aqueous outflow system. The intraocular pressure is maintained by the balance of aqueous humor production-secreted by the ciliary body- and its drainage through two pathways: the trabecular meshwork (in anterior chamber) and the uveoscleral outflow route.^[6]

Figure 1. "Structures of the Eye Labeled" by Chiara Mazzasette is licensed under CC BY 4.0 / A derivative from the original work)

OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA

Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) is the most common type of glaucoma, responsible for over 80% of cases in western population. The term ‘angle’ refers to the space between iris and cornea, which remains open in both healthy eyes and those affected by POAG. This anatomical space allows the aqueous humor to access the trabecular meshwork and drain into the Schlemm’s canal.^[3]

Open-angle glaucoma is a chronic, progressive optic neuropathy with multiple contributing factors. It is characterized by an open anterior chamber angle, changes in the optic nerve head, thinning of the retinal nerve fiber layer, and a gradual loss of peripheral vision. If left untreated, the condition can lead to central vision impairment and complete blindness.^[4] IOP is an important risk factor and the target for therapy when treating patients.

The disease is usually bilateral, but asymmetry depends on the etiology. While elevated IOP is a key factor, it does not always result in glaucoma or optic nerve damage. Some individuals with ocular hypertension (IOP>21 mmHg) may maintain a normal visual field and healthy optic nerve without developing the disease. Clinically, OAG is diagnosed by the open angle, IOP > 21 mm Hg and loss of visual field associated with the degeneration of ganglion cell axons (“optic neuropathy”).^[5]

In patients with open-angle glaucoma, there is increased resistance to aqueous outflow through the trabecular meshwork. In contrast, the access to the drainage pathways is obstructed typically by the iris in patients with angle-closure glaucoma.^[6]

RISK FACTORS:

- Older age (African American, 40+ years; Caucasians, 65+ years)
- Race (African-American, Afro- Caribbean, and West African patients have a 4-fold increased risk of developing OAG)

- Family history (eg. the Rotterdam Eye study found a 9.2 times higher risk of developing OAG if first degree relatives had glaucoma)
- Elevated IOP
- Myopia (eg. results from studies have reported an increased risk of glaucoma of up to 20% for each diopter increase in myopia).^[4]

Figure 2: glaucoma. Evidence of previous surgery: This child's eye is blind from (Centre for Eye Healthiridectomy). © Clare Gilbert. International www.iceh.org.uk, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine.

ANGLE-CLOSURE GLAUCOMA

Angle-closure glaucoma is a condition classified as a medical emergency that develops when the anterior chamber angle progressively narrows, restricting the drainage of aqueous humor. This leads to increase of IOP, which, if left untreated, can result in a damage of the optic nerve. Acute form of this condition occurs when this narrowing suddenly interrupt the passage of aqueous humor in trabecular meshwork, causing a rapid rise in IOP. Symptoms include: severe eye pain, headache, nausea, vomiting, blurred vision and halos around lights. Chronic form, on the other hand, involves intermittent obstruction of the drainage pathway, gradually leading to a scarring and further narrowing of the angle Over time, this condition can cause the formation of the peripheral anterior synechiae and permanent adhesion between the iris and trabecular meshwork, thus preventing correct outflow and contributing to persistently high IOP.⁷ Epidemiological studies estimate that about one in every 40 individuals over the age of 40 experiences glaucoma-related vision impairment. Globally, approximately 60 millions people are affected, with 8.4 million suffering from bilateral blindness due to the disease.

Despite continuous progress in healthcare, nearly half of glaucoma cases remain undiagnosed, even in developed nations. Since glaucoma is often asymptomatic until significant vision loss occurs, early detection remains a crucial challenge; once vision is lost due to glaucoma, it cannot be restored. For this reason, it is crucial to improve screening and diagnostic strategies.^[2]

Assessment includes a fundoscopic examination, visual field testing, tonometry, optical coherence tomography (OCT), and gonioscopy. Glaucoma diagnosis relies on identifying progressive optic neuropathy and/or visual field defects, often in conjunction with elevated IOP. Ocular hypertension is diagnosed in individuals with IOP levels exceeding 21 mmHg.^[1]

CLINIC CASE

Vision-related quality of life (VRQoL) reflects how vision affects daily activities, social life, and emotions. A study in Italy found that VRQoL can improve as people adapt to vision loss and accept their condition (Riva et al., 2019). Research shows that VRQoL declines as glaucoma worsens but usually only when the visual field index (VFI) in the better eye drops below 50%.^[11]

Methods: Responses from 1182 participants were analyzed, comparing those with and without self-reported glaucoma. Questionnaires assessed vision-related quality of life (NEI VFQ-25), general health (SF-36), physical activity, socioeconomic status, and alcohol/tobacco use. Balance tests and BMI were also measured. Among them, 560 were randomly selected for an ophthalmic exam. Data were analyzed separately for known and confirmed glaucoma, ocular hypertension, and previously undiagnosed cases.

Results: Both conventional and Rasch analysis of the NEI VFQ- 25 questionnaire suggest that individuals who self-reported having glaucoma experience a lower vision related quality of life (VRQoL) ($p=0.003/p=0.024$). However, when considering overall quality of life (QoL), there were no significant differences between those with and without glaucoma, except for a decline in self-reported general health among glaucoma patients ($p=0.01$).

A logistic regression analysis was conducted to explore potential predictors of poor VRQoL. While glaucoma itself was not found to be a statistically significant factor, low household income showed a strong association with reduced VRQoL. Other factors such as socioeconomic background, physical activity levels, and lifestyle choices were generally similar between individuals with and without glaucoma. Additionally, among those who underwent a clinical eye exam, no notable differences in VRQoL were found between individuals diagnosed with glaucoma and those without the condition.^[11]

GLAUCOMA THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES

1. Pharmacological Therapy:

- Topical Medications: the primary treatment for glaucoma involves eye drops such as prostaglandin analogs, betablockers, and carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, which lower intraocular pressure (IOP).
- Oral Medications: carbonic anhydrase inhibitors are used when topical treatments are insufficient.^[12]

2. Laser Therapy:

- Selective Laser Trabeculoplasty (SLT): SLT improves aqueous humor outflow and is a first-line treatment for lowering IOP.
- Laser Cyclophotocoagulation: a more invasive option, used in advanced or refractory cases.^[13]

3. Surgical Interventions:

- Trabeculectomy: a surgical procedure that creates a new drainage channel for aqueous humor, highly effective but with risks of complications.

- Minimally Invasive Glaucoma Surgery (MIGS): includes techniques like the iStent, offering lower complication rates.^[14]

4. Emerging Therapies:

- Gene Therapy and Stem Cells: ongoing research explores genetic modifications to lower IOP long-term and stem cell therapies for optic nerve regeneration.^[15]

TREATMENT

Glaucoma often has no symptoms in its early stages, so many cases go undiagnosed. Detecting it early can help prevent vision loss, but current screening methods face challenges due to imperfect tests and low disease prevalence. Opportunistic screening, like checking for glaucoma during eye exams for other conditions, is limited by false positives and negatives. However, new technologies like polygenic risk scores (PRS) and artificial intelligence (AI) show promise in improving detection by assessing individual risk and accurately identifying signs of the disease.^[8]

Targeted glaucoma screenings in populations with high levels of poverty and high proportions of people who identify as African American or Hispanic/Latino identified a 27% rate of glaucoma and suspected glaucoma, which is 3 times the national average. In 2019, Columbia University, the University of Michigan, and the University of Alabama at Birmingham received CDC funding to explore how telehealth could help detect glaucoma in high-risk communities. Their goal was to reach people who are most at risk but have the least access to eye care. Across the three studies, 2,379 people participated, and 27% screened positive for glaucoma or were suspected of having it—three times the national average. Most participants were over 40, with a majority identifying as African American, Hispanic/Latino, or female. Many had low income, limited education, or no health insurance. These findings highlight the importance of targeted screenings in underserved communities.^[9]

Family history is a useful indicator of genetic risk for glaucoma. The disease and its related traits are highly heritable, making awareness of family history an important tool in preventing blindness. Studies show that first-degree relatives of glaucoma patients have a significantly higher risk—22% in the Rotterdam Study and 40% in the Glaucoma Inheritance Study in Tasmania. Therefore, cascade clinical screening can be an effective strategy for detecting undiagnosed glaucoma.^[10]

CONCLUSION

Glaucoma is a major cause of irreversible vision loss, but effectively screening for the disease remain a technical challenge. Advances in technology, such as polygenic risk scores (PRS) and artificial intelligence (AI), have the potential to enhance early detection by identifying individuals at higher risk of vision loss. These innovations could make glaucoma screening more practical and improve outcomes by enabling earlier intervention.^[16]

References list:

1. Dietze J, Blair K, Zeppieri M, Havens SJ. Glaucoma. 2024 Mar 16. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 30855805.
2. Quigley HA. Glaucoma. *Lancet*. 2011 Apr 16;377(9774):1367-77. doi: 10.1016/S01406736(10)61423-7. Epub 2011 Mar 30. PMID: 21453963.
3. Križaj D. What is glaucoma? 2019 May 30. In: Kolb H, Fernandez E, Nelson R, editors. *Webvision: The Organization of the Retina and Visual System* [Internet]. Salt Lake City (UT): University of Utah Health Sciences Center; 1995-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK543075/>
4. Mahabadi N, Zeppieri M, Tripathy K. Open Angle Glaucoma. 2024 Mar 7. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 28722917.
5. Dave SD, Zeppieri M, Meyer JJ. Chronic Closed Angle Glaucoma. 2024 Jan 25. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 32644524
6. Weinreb RN, Aung T, Medeiros FA. The pathophysiology and treatment of glaucoma: a review. *JAMA*. 2014 May 14;311(18):1901-11. doi: 10.1001/jama.2014.3192. PMID: 24825645; PMCID: PMC4523637.
7. Dave SD, Zeppieri M, Meyer JJ. Chronic Closed Angle Glaucoma. [Updated 2024 Jan 25]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559098/#>
8. Founti P, Stuart K, Nolan WP, Khawaja AP, Foster PJ. Screening Strategies and Methodologies. *J Glaucoma*. 2024 Aug 1;33(Suppl 1):S15-S20. Doi 10.1097/IJG.0000000000002426. Epub 2024 Aug 19. PMID: 39149948.
9. Newman-Casey PA, Hark LA, Lu MC, Nghiem VTH, Swain T, McGwin G Jr, Sapru S, Girkin C, Owsley C. Social Determinants of Health and Glaucoma Screening and Detection in the SIGHT Studies. *J Glaucoma*. 2024 Aug 1;33(Suppl 1):S60-S65. doi: 10.1097/IJG.0000000000002398. Epub 2024 Apr 5. PMID: 38573889; PMCID: PMC11613646.
10. Mackey DA, Bigirimana D, Staffieri SE. Integrating Genetics in Glaucoma Screening. *J Glaucoma*. 2024 Aug 1;33(Suppl 1):S49S53. doi: 10.1097/IJG.0000000000002425. Epub 2024 Aug 19. PMID: 39149951; PMCID: PMC11332373.
11. Johansson LH, Kalaboukhova L, Erhag HF, Skoog I, Zetterberg M. Vision-related quality of life among 70-year-olds diagnosed with glaucoma. *Acta Ophthalmol*. 2024 Mar;102(2):201-207. doi: 10.1111/aos.15737. Epub 2023 Aug 2. PMID: 37533157.
12. Bluwol E. Traitement des glaucomes [Glaucoma treatment]. *Rev Prat*. 2016 May;66(5):508-513. French. PMID: 30512573.
13. Ma A, Yu SWY, Wong JKW. Micropulse laser for the treatment of glaucoma: A literature review. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 2019 Jul-Aug;64(4):486-497. doi: 10.1016/j.survophthal.2019.01.001. Epub 2019 Jan 11. PMID: 30639207.
14. Sunaric

- Megevand G, Bron AM. Personalising surgical treatments for glaucoma patients. *Prog Retin Eye Res.* 2021 Mar;81:100879. doi: 10.1016/j.preteyeres.2020.100879. Epub 2020 Jun 18. PMID: 32562883.
15. Lee HP, Tsung TH, Tsai YC, Chen YH, Lu DW. Glaucoma: Current and New Therapeutic Approaches. *Biomedicines.* 2024 Sep 3;12(9):2000. doi: 10.3390/biomedicines12092000. PMID: 39335514; PMCID: PMC11429057.
 16. Founti P, Stuart K, Nolan WP, Khawaja AP, Foster PJ. Screening Strategies and Methodologies. *J Glaucoma.* 2024 Aug 1;33(Suppl 1):S15S20. doi: 10.1097/IJG.0000000000002426. Epub 2024 Aug 19. PMID: 39149948.

